

REDUCING MANUFACTURING COSTS BY DIRECT ROVING PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Direct Roving Placement technology (DRP) is presented as an upcoming technology for the automated production of dry fibre composite preforms. Primary objective of the DRP technology is the reduction of the overall manufacturing costs, mainly by lowering the material costs. This can be achieved by directly processing raw fibre material combined with an online application of appropriate binders for the fibre fixation. This makes preceding fabric manufacturing processes as well as material wasting cutting processes unnecessary. One of the key technologies for a successful introduction of DRP technologies, a focus of this paper and the ongoing research, is the binder application, the binders themselves and their influence on the process and the material. Furthermore, the research activities are aiming for high production rates and improved overall manufacturing quality with an automated high volume direct fibre layup process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Being a part of the Institute of Composite Structures and Adaptive Systems (FA) of the German Aerospace Center (DLR e.V.), the Centre for Lightweight-Production-Technology (ZLP) in Stade performs general research in the field of automated fibre composite manufacturing technologies. One field of research that has been growing at the ZLP over the last years is the development of new production technologies for large scale composite parts such as aircraft fuselage shells or wind turbine rotor blades. Especially new projects in the wind energy sector called for improvements in the automation of rotor blade production. The goals are higher production rates, improved part quality and lower production costs. To reach these objectives, the DLR is focusing on the development of a new manufacturing technology called Direct Roving Placement (DRP). The DRP technology, as well as a complete toolset for the production of a 20 m prototype rotor blade, are being developed in ongoing projects. As an expected goal of these projects, nearly the whole process chain from design, preform building up to the final infusion of big parts, will be covered by the departments of the FA Institute. Therefore this paper will cover the DRP technology with a focus on the production of wind energy rotor blades.

2 STATE OF THE ART

In the state of the art manufacturing process, a large part of the rotor blade production is done manually. There are a few parts of the fiber layup process that are semi-automated. More common is the complete manual layup of pre-cut pieces that are as big as 130 m² and more. Manufacturing of large rotor blades allows the parallel work of multiple workers at the same time in one tool. The result is a quite high production rate of up to 2000 kg/h, even though the layup is done manually. However, this comes with a big disadvantage in fiber alignment accuracy and overall manufacturing quality. The rotor blades cause up to 20% of the total costs of a wind turbine. For large blades, 6-digit sums are reached easily. Main costs for the rotor blades with up to 60% are the material costs. Costs arising from damage to wind turbine blades that could be avoided by a quality-assured automated production cannot be quantified. Moreover, the resulting loss of image should not be underestimated.

2.1 Cost study

Both, the resin and the fibers determine the main part of the total material costs. Large blades are already made of up to 15 tons of fibers and more. This means that even small amounts of cost reduction per kilogram fiber can be worth an effort. A closer look on the process chain that a raw glass fiber roving is going through until it is laid up into a rotor blade tool, shows some options where cost savings are possible.

Figure 1 shows the different processes involved. The first one is the transformation of the roving into a non-crimped fabric (NCF). This is done by huge and complex high-tech knitting machines. The production of a NCF with such a machine already leads to 1-3 % of fibers being wasted. Next the NCFs are cut according to a corresponding plybook. This causes another 5-10 % of fibers being wasted. Finally the pre-cut NCFs are ready to be laid down into the rotor blade tool. [2]

Figure 1: State of the art for the manufacturing chain of wind turbine blades.

The DRP technology makes the process of producing a NCF and cutting it obsolete (see next chapter). Therefore, the costs for expensive knitting machines and cutting tables as well as the costs for the logistics and the loss of value by producing waste can be saved. Current predictions and price information for glass rovings and standard glass NCFs used for rotor blade production show, that savings of about 1 €/kg fibers are realistic. For carbon fibers, the savings per kilogram will even be higher. However, due to a broad range of different materials, specific production examples need to be looked at in detail in order to get realistic numbers for carbon fibers.

3 DIRECT ROVING PLACEMENT TECHNOLOGY

One of the challenges of the Direct Roving Placement method is the safe fixation of the fibers after placement. A sketch of the DRP method that is being developed at the ZLP can be seen in Figure 2. Multiple rovings are fed into a fiber guide, get homogeneously arranged next to each other until finally being applied unidirectionally like a tape to the tool surface. Shortly before the fibers get in contact with the surface, a binder application unit applies an adhesive onto the tool surface or already laid down fibers. Finally, pressure is applied by a compaction roller in order to improve the fixation process. Additional heat could be applied if needed for better results. The technology allows completely free fiber angle orientations.

Figure 2: The Direct Roving Placement method

Starting point for further development is a robot based dry carbon fiber application unit, engineered by the German startup Compositence GmbH, Stuttgart. The unit is designed for directly manufacturing three-dimensional near net shaped carbon fiber preforms. At the ZLP, the unit will be modified in order to work with raw glass fibers and it will be upgraded with an online binder application unit. Next to the modification of components in order to reliably work with glass fibers, the online binder application and its influence on following production processes as well as the influence on mechanical properties of finished parts will be one of the main work packages.

3.1 Binder application

A variety of binders as well as different application methods are available. The requirements for an online application method for full 3D preforms put spraying techniques into focus. These allow an even distribution of the binder without any relevant influence of the gravity, when applying material on vertical surfaces. Spraying techniques also allow a wide variety of different application patterns, from droplets to spider webs or full cover. The main influences are the binder's physical properties, the application temperature, the pressure used for spraying and the nozzle geometry. Aim of the DRP method is to use a combination of a suitable binder with an appropriate application unit in order to make additional heating units unnecessary. This could further increase the overall process productivity, since state of the art heating units combined with already applied binders with high melting points often lead to a reduction of the dynamic of the layup process.

3.2 Evaluation of common binders

Different preforming binders were experimentally investigated and evaluated. Well performing binders should feature low wash-out effects during resin infusion, high peeling strength of the preforms, easy processibility with no or only minor negative effects on the mechanical performance. Keeping these parameters in mind, at first, the compatibilities of the binders with the epoxy resin system were investigated with varying chemical composition and concentration of the binders. Then, dry preforms, with binder being applied, have been tested. Afterwards, the corresponding composite

laminates were fabricated using the vacuum assisted resin infusion technology (VARI). These were used to study the effect of the binders on the mechanical properties of finished composite parts. For each binder that has been tested, test sheets with a binder concentration of 1% and 3% (weight percentage) have been produced. Afterwards, the tension, shear and compression properties were determined using transvers and longitudinal load cases. Table 1 summarizes the examined powder binder systems, varying in the chemical composition and thermal properties.

No.	binder type	abbreviation	melting range [°C]	peak [°C]	powder particle size (x_{50}) [μm]
1	polyhydroxyether	phenoxy	amorphous	amorphous	59,5
2	polyester	PES	33-62	58	60,2
3	co-polyamide	Co-PA	75-96	89	42,4
4	co-polyamide	Co-PA	104-155	129	52,0
5	co-polyester	Co-PES	97-160	133	59,5
6	co-polyester	Co-PES	87-133	107	57,0
7	epoxy	EP	52-66	61	59,0

Table 1: Summary of the binders used in this study

Applying viscometry, DSC and reflected light microscopy, the number of binders could be narrowed down to the system of phenoxy, the two Co-PA systems and the Co-PES No. 6. The other binders showed material and process incompatibilities and therefore were excluded from further tests.

Testing the dry preforms showed, that an average peel strength of about 10 - 12 N/cm could be achieved. The mechanical tests revealed a strong correlation between decreased performance of the samples and the amount of binder used. For example, the compressive strength in fiber direction of the Co-PES No. 6 used at a fraction of 3% is reduced by about 40% compared to the reference value of 763 MPa (no binder applied). The same test with the other binders showed an average reduction of 5% - 10%. The only exception was the phenoxy binder. With this system, the compression strength transversely to the fiber direction even increased by about 15% (reference value = 135 MPa, binder weight fraction = 1%). The corresponding stiffness also increased by about 30% (reference value = 11.9 GPa). Small differences in fiber volume fraction have to be taken into consideration. A dependency of the binder type and binder content on the composite performance is shown in Figure 3.

These results give a hint on the performance and usability of common binders. All binders in this study were used in powder form. Their high viscosity is not an ideal property for good sprayability, even though melting them with high enough temperatures would make that possible. Current and future research will focus on further low viscosity binder systems.

Figure 3: Depictive representation of the performance characteristics of the investigated binders

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

When the DRP technology is performing robustly, an increase of its productivity will be the next big goal. The first prototype will have a limited fiber application width of 192 mm. The unit's productivity in kilograms per hour, depending on layer thickness and the average application speed, can be seen in Figure 4. The robots unit maximum speed is around 1.5 meters per second. However, the real average application speed will strongly depend on the geometry that is laid up and will be a lot slower. The layer thickness (g/m^2), that also has an enormous influence on the productivity, is mainly determined by the part design and therefore can also be varied only within tight limits.

Figure 4: A look on the productivity and its most important influences

After the successful implementation of the technology at the ZLP, further improvements will be needed in order to make this new method ready for real rotor blade production. This includes, among other things, the development of a fully functional production plant concept. For this purpose, it is planned to use mobile robot units at the ZLP in the future. The flexibility of a mobile Direct Roving Placement robot will allow several units to work efficiently together on a single rotor blade tool. Thus, the overall productivity will be increased. In addition, further improvements of the placement unit like an increased application width and the ability to apply thicker layers, will also benefit the productivity. The influence of the application width on productivity at a given specific layer weight is shown in Figure 5. In the future, a productivity of 2000 kg/h could be achieved by the use of an increased number of DRP units as well as improvements of the units themselves. Once the process reliably works and the benefits of a load path aligned fiber orientation as well as the possibility for completely flexible layer architectures regarding the blade design are fully taken into account, lighter and more efficient rotor blade designs are possible which would lead to even more material savings.

Figure 5: A comparison of the productivity for different application widths

Furthermore, application tests with a promising new binder system have been made and also first test sheets have been produced with it. These results will be discussed in the final presentation.

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